

Calibration of Numerical Analyses of Compacted Granular Fills with Mohr-Coulomb and Hardening Soil Models: Comparison of Elastic Rebound and DIN 18134 Methods

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Kasım Polat: 2026

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Abstract: *In this study, the parameters of the Mohr-Coulomb (MC) and Hardening Soil (HS) models for a compacted granular fill layer (GW) were calibrated using data from two different static plate loading tests (with 5 and 4 loading-unloading cycles) carried out on a road construction site in an organized industrial zone. The stiffness parameters of the soil were determined by two different methods:*

the elastic rebound theory based on elastic settlements during loading-unloading cycles, and the deformation modulus (E_v) calculated according to the DIN 18134 standard.

The elasticity moduli obtained from both methods were used directly as input in the MC model. For the HS model, the primary loading modulus (E_{50}^{ref}) and the unloading/reloading modulus (E_{ur}^{ref}) were determined using typical ratios from the literature. The internal friction angle of the granular layer was taken as $\phi = 40^\circ$, and the dilatancy angle as $\psi = 10^\circ$.

The resulting parameter sets were modeled in Plaxis 3D, and the calculated settlements were compared with field measurements. The results showed that the elastic rebound method yields higher stiffness values, whereas the DIN 18134 method provides more realistic settlement predictions. This study highlights the influence of different calibration approaches on numerical model outcomes and emphasizes the importance of method selection in engineering practice.

Keywords: *Static, Plate, load, Mohr-Coulomb, Hardening Soil, Elastic rebound, DIN 18134, Plaxis 3D, Numerical, Analysis.*

Date Of Submission: xx-xx-xxxx

Date Of Acceptance: xx-xx-xxxx

1. INTRODUCTION

Realistic modeling of soil-structure interaction using the finite element method depends on the constitutive model employed and the accuracy of its parameters. Compacted granular fills are often represented by the Mohr-Coulomb (MC) or Hardening Soil (HS) models. While the MC model is widely used due to its simplicity, the HS model better captures stress-dependent stiffness and loading-unloading behavior (Schanz, Vermeer, & Bonnier, 1999). The internal friction angle of granular soils is one of the most important parameters determining shear strength. It is known from the literature that the ϕ value for dense granular soils generally ranges between 35° and 45° (Bolton, 1986); (Meyerhof, 1959). In this study, $\phi = 40^\circ$ and $\psi = 10^\circ$ were adopted for the compacted gravel fill.

The plate loading test is one of the most common field tests used to determine the deformation and bearing capacity characteristics of soils in situ. The load-settlement curves obtained from the test can be evaluated by different methods to understand the mechanical behavior of the soil. Two different evaluation methods were used in this study.

Elastic rebound theory: The modulus of elasticity (E), shear modulus (G), and modulus of subgrade reaction (C_z) of the soil are calculated using the elastic settlements during loading-unloading cycles. This method reflects the purely elastic behavior of the soil and is particularly associated with the unloading/reloading modulus (E_{ur}) (Barkan, 2013); (DAS, 2010).

DIN 18134 deformation modulus (E_v): This standard calculates a secant modulus from the slope of the stress-displacement curve between $0.3\sigma_{max}$ and $0.7\sigma_{max}$. E_v values are widely used for assessing soil compactness and quality control (DIN, 2012-04).

Several studies exist in the literature on the calibration of MC and HS models using data from plate loading tests. (Brinkgreve, Kumarswamy, & Swolfs, 2016) provided comprehensive explanations regarding the implementation of the HS model in Plaxis software. Waterman showed that E_v values can be used to determine HS model parameters. (Jawad, Al-Rumaithi, & Fattah, 2020) successfully simulated plate loading tests in Plaxis

3D using the MC model. However, only a limited number of studies have compared the elastic rebound theory and the DIN 18134 method on the same field data. This study aims to fill that gap.

The objective of this study is to compare the MC and HS model parameters obtained from the elastic rebound and DIN 18134 methods using the same field data, evaluate the performance of these parameters in Plaxis 3D analyses, and provide recommendations for engineering practice.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD

2.1 Test site and soil properties

The test site is a road construction site in an organized industrial zone. The soil profile consists of two layers. A schematic representation of the road cross-section at the test site is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic road cross-section of the test site.

Sublayer: High-plasticity silt (MH) improved with 3.5% hydraulic lime. This layer consists of a total of 12 lifts, each 50 cm thick, reaching a total height of 6 m. Each lift was compacted using a steel-banded roller compactor. Compaction control was carried out with a Troxler nuclear gauge, and a minimum compaction ratio of 95% was achieved. The soil properties of the sublayer are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Properties of high-plasticity silt (MH).

Parameter	Value
Natural unit weight γ_n (kN/m ³)	21.3
Dry unit weight γ_k (kN/m ³)	18.9
Average water content (%w)	12.18
Clay and silt content (%)	54.90
(LL) Liquid Limit (%)	61.18
(PL) Plastic limit (%)	48.68
(PI) Plasticity index (%)	12.50

The strength parameters of the sublayer were determined by the unconfined compression test, as shown in Figure 2. The maximum stress was measured as $q_u=1310$ kPa. Cohesion is calculated from the unconfined compressive strength using Equation 1 (Craig, 1974):

$$c = \frac{q_u}{2} \quad (1)$$

From this, the cohesion was found to be $c=655$ kN/m². The modulus of elasticity E_{50} was calculated from the linear portion of the curve using Equation 2. The stress corresponding to 50% of the maximum stress, $\sigma_{50}=655$ kPa, and the strain at this point, $\varepsilon_{50}\approx 0.0182$ were read. Accordingly

$$E_{50} = \frac{650 \text{ kN/m}^2}{0.0182} = 36 \text{ MPa} \quad (2)$$

In the Plaxis 3D modeling, the Poisson's ratio for the sublayer was taken as $\nu = 0.3$ (selected as a typical value for silt), the internal friction angle as $\phi = 30^\circ$ (commonly adopted for consolidated clayey soils), and the dilatancy angle as $\psi = 0$ (Bowles J. E., 1997); (Plaxis, 2023).

Upper layer: Uniformly graded gravel (GW) fill material with a thickness of 25 cm, placed over the sublayers. It was laid in two lifts and compacted using a steel-banded roller compactor. The static plate loading tests were performed on this granular layer. The soil properties of the granular layer are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Properties of uniformly graded gravel (GW) fill.

Parameter	Değer
Natural unit weight γ_n (kN/m ³)	23.6
Dry unit weight γ_k (kN/m ³)	22.9
Average water content (%w)	0.74
Clay & silt content (%)	2.03
Plasticity	NonPlastik
Internal friction angle, ϕ	40°
Dilatancy angle, ψ	10°

During the compaction controls performed in the field, the relative density was determined as $D_r \geq 96$ in all layers. The empirical relationship given in Equation 3, proposed by (Meyerhof, 1959) for the relationship between the internal friction angle (ϕ) and relative density (D_r) of granular soils, was used.

$$\phi = \phi_{min} + (\phi_{max} - \phi_{min})D_r \quad (3)$$

Here, ϕ_{min} is the internal friction angle of loose soil (typically 30°), and ϕ_{max} is the internal friction angle of very dense soil (typically 45°) (Bowles J. E., 1997). For $D_r=0.96$:

$$\phi = 30^0 + (45^0 - 30^0) * 0.96 = 44,4^0 \quad (4)$$

However, taking into account previous calibration studies and typical values in the literature, $\phi=40^0$ was used in this study. For the dilatancy angle, the relationship proposed by (Bolton, 1986) was adopted:

$$\psi = \phi - 30^0 \quad (5)$$

From this, $\psi=10^0$ was adopted. Although cohesion is generally negligible for granular fills, a very small value ($c=10$ kN/m²) was assigned to enhance numerical stability (Plaxis, 2023). Poisson's ratio was taken as $\nu=0.3$.

Figure 2. Unconfined compression test graph of the sublayer MH class soil improved with 3.5% hydraulic lime (at the end of the 6th day)

The static plate loading test is one of the most established field tests used to determine the deformation and bearing capacity characteristics of soils in situ. The load-settlement curves obtained from the test can be evaluated using different methods to understand the mechanical behavior of the soil and to determine the parameters required for numerical models.

The tests were carried out with a 30 cm diameter circular plate in accordance with DIN 18134. Unloading was applied after each loading step. The plate area is $A=0.0707 \text{ m}^2$. The maximum applied stress (q) and measured settlement (s) values for both tests are given in Table 3, and the load-deformation graph of the test is also presented in figure 3 and figure 4.

Table 3. Maximum applied stress and corresponding settlements in the tests

Loading No	5 Loading test q		4 Loading test q	
	(kN/m ²)	S (mm)	(kN/m ²)	S (mm)
1	2.47	0.90	2.47	0.48
2	4.95	1.36	4.95	0.79
3	7.42	2.11	7.42	1,21
4	14.85	4.75	14.85	2.68
5	17.32	6.17	-	-

Figure 3. Load-deformation graphs of the 4-loading (a) and 5-loading (b) static plate loading tests performed in the field

Elastic rebound theory is based on the elastic behavior of the soil during loading-unloading cycles. In each loading step, the difference between the total settlement (s) and the permanent settlement remaining after unloading is defined as the elastic settlement (s_e). This elastic settlement represents the fully reversible deformation of the soil. In this study, the elastic settlement values for each loading step were taken directly from the test reports (Table 4).

The subgrade reaction coefficient C_z is defined as the ratio of the applied stress to the elastic settlement: As seen in Figure 4, for each loading step in the test, the elastic settlement ($s_{e(i)}$) is determined as the difference between the total settlement and the permanent settlement remaining after unloading. Subsequently, a graph of q versus $s_{e(i)}$ is plotted, and the slope of this graph gives the subgrade reaction coefficient $C_z = q/s_e$. The spring constant is then:

Figure 4. Nature of load-settlement diagram for cyclic plate load test (a) & load versus elastic rebound (b)

$$k_{plate} = \frac{qA}{s_c} \tag{6}$$

is calculated using the formula (DAS, 2010). Here, A is the plate area. As theoretically shown by (Barkan, 2013), the following relationship exists between the subgrade reaction coefficient and the modulus of elasticity:

$$C_z = \frac{q}{S_e} = 1.13 \frac{E}{(1 - \nu^2) \sqrt{A}} \quad (7)$$

Here, ν is Poisson's ratio. Since the shear modulus is $G=E/[2(1+\nu)]$, rearranging Equation (10):

$$G = \frac{(1-\nu)C_z\sqrt{A}}{2.26} \quad (8)$$

Elasticity modulus:

$$E_{rebound} = 2G * (1 + \nu) \quad (9)$$

is calculated using the equation. The $E_{rebound}$ obtained by this method represents the elastic stiffness of the soil under unloading/reloading conditions. In this study, elastic settlements were determined for both tests, and the calculated parameters are given in Table 4 and Figure 5. Poisson's ratio was taken as $\nu=0,3$ in the calculations.

Table 4. Parameters calculated using the elastic rebound theory for the 4-loading and 5-loading tests

Test No	C_z (kg/cm ²)	G (kg/cm ²)	$E_{rebound}$ (Mpa)
4	175	1440	366.8
5	87	713	181.9

Figure 5. q-s_e graphs of settlements calculated according to the elastic rebound theory for the 5 loading (a) and 4 loading (b) tests.

2.2 Calculation of deformation modulus (E_v) according to DIN 18134

According to the DIN 18134 standard, the deformation modulus (E_v for each loading step is calculated from the slope of the linear portion of the stress-displacement curve between 0.3σ_{max} and 0.7σ_{max} (DIN, 2012-04). Using the stress increase Δσ = 0.4σ_{max} within this range and the corresponding settlement increase Δs (mm):

$$E_v = \frac{\Delta\sigma}{\Delta s} D(1 - \nu^2)I \tag{10}$$

Here, D is the plate diameter (0.3 m), ν is Poisson's ratio (0.3), and I is the shape factor for a circular rigid plate (π/4≈0.785). The unit of Δσ is kg/cm²; when conversion to kPa is required in the formula, the conversion factor 1 kg/cm²=100 kPa is used. Δs is in mm.

The calculated E_v values for both tests were obtained using the 0.7σ_{max} – 0.3σ_{max} range and the corresponding settlement values for the relevant loading steps. The calculation results are presented in Tables 5 and 6.

Table 5. E_v values according to DIN 18134 for the 5 loading test

Loading No	0.7σ _{max} (kg/cm ²)	0.3σ _{max} (kg/cm ²)	S(0.7Δσ _{max}) (cm)	S(0.3Δσ _{max}) (cm)	Δσ (kg/cm ²)	ΔS (cm)	E _v (Mpa)	E _{vn} /E _{vn-1}
1	1.73	0.74	0.58	0.02	0.99	0.038	66	1.6
2	3.46	1.48	0.11	0.07	1.98	0.040	106	1.1
3	5.20	2.23	0.158	0.10	2.97	0.058	115	1.1
4	10.39	4.45	0.30	0.19	5.94	0.110	124	1.1
5	12.13	5.20	0.495	0.38	6.93	0.115	130	

Table 6. E_v values according to DIN18134 for the 4 loading test

Loading No	0.7 σ_{max} (kg/cm2)	0.3 σ_{max} (kg/cm2)	S(0.7 $\Delta\sigma_{max}$) (cm)	S(0.3 $\Delta\sigma_{max}$) (cm)	$\Delta\sigma$ (kg/cm2)	ΔS (cm)	E_v (Mpa)	E_{vn}/E_{vn-1}
1	1.73	0.74	0.031	0.01	0.99	0.021	66	1.8
2	3.46	1.48	0.058	0.04	1.98	0.018	106	1.1
3	5.20	2.23	0.091	0.06	2.97	0.031	115	1.0
4	10.39	4.45	0.173	0.12	5.94	0.053	124	0

2.3 Theory and parameters of Mohr-Coulomb Model

The Mohr-Coulomb (MC) model is one of the most widely used constitutive models in geotechnical engineering. The model is based on the work of Charles-Augustin de Coulomb and Christian Otto Mohr and was developed to describe the shear strength of soil and rock materials (Labuz & Zang, 2012).

The Mohr-Coulomb failure criterion assumes that failure occurs when the shear stress (τ) on a plane is linearly dependent on the normal stress (σ) on the same plane (Coulomb, 1776).

$$\tau = c - \sigma \tan(\phi) \quad (11)$$

Here, c is the cohesion and ϕ is the internal friction angle. Using the Mohr circle, the expression in terms of principal stresses at failure (Mohr, 1900) is:

$$\frac{\sigma_1 - \sigma_3}{2} = c \cos(\phi) + \frac{\sigma_1 + \sigma_3}{2} \sin(\phi) \quad (12)$$

In the MC model, elastic behavior is described by the theory of linear isotropic elasticity (Timoshenko & Goodier, 1970). Two fundamental parameters are required for elastic behavior: the modulus of elasticity (E) and Poisson's ratio (ν).

In this study, two different values were used for the modulus of elasticity E in the MC model:

- (i) $E_{rebound}$ obtained from the elastic rebound theory (Table 4), and
- (ii) the E_v value at the final loading step according to DIN 18134 (for the 5-loading test, $E_v=130$ MPa in Table 5; for the 4-loading test, $E_v=252$ MPa in Table 6).

The rationale for this choice is that the MC model must represent the entire loading range with a single E value. The E_v value at the highest stress level (maximum load) reflects the stiffness of the soil in its most compacted

state and is the most appropriate value to represent the behavior under the design load in practice (Bowles J. E., 1997). The other parameters are as given in Section 2.1. The MC parameters are summarized in Table 7.

Table 7. MC model parameters (based on elastic rebound and DIN 18134)

Parameters	Unit	5 Loading	5 Loading	4 Loading	4 Loading	Sub Base
		(Erebound)	(E _{v5} -DIN18134)	(Erebound)	(E _{v4} -DIN18134)	
φ (°)	derece	40	40	40	40	30
ψ (°)	derece	10	10	10	10	0
C	kN/m ²	10	10	10	10	655
E	MPa	181.9	130	366.8	252	36
v	-	0,3	0,3	0,3	0,3	0,3

2.4 Hardening Soil Modeli ve rijitlik parametreleri

The Hardening Soil (HS) model was developed by (Schanz, Vermeer, & Bonnier, 1999) and models the stress-dependent stiffness behavior of soils in a more realistic manner. The model includes three different stiffness parameters: the primary loading stiffness (E_{50}), the oedometric modulus (E_{oed}), and the unloading/reloading stiffness (E_{ur}). All of these parameters are stress-dependent and are defined under a reference stress ($p_{ref}=100$ kPa):

$$E_{50} = E_{50}^{ref} \left(\frac{p'}{p_{ref}} \right)^m \quad (13)$$

$$E_{oed} = E_{oed}^{ref} \left(\frac{p'}{p_{ref}} \right)^m \quad (14)$$

$$E_{ur} = E_{ur}^{ref} \left(\frac{p'}{p_{ref}} \right)^m \quad (15)$$

Here; p' is the mean effective stress, and m is the stress dependency exponent. For granular soils, m is generally taken as 0.5 (Schanz, Vermeer, & Bonnier, 1999). The failure ratio R_f is typically 0.9 (Plaxis, 2023).

The following considerations were taken into account in determining the HS model parameters:

Selection of E_{50}^{ref} : The literature states that in HS model calibration, the E_{50}^{ref} value can be determined from the secant modulus at the initial part of the primary loading curve (e.g., from the E_{v1} value) (Waterman, (Brinkgreve, Kumarswamy, & Swolfs, 2016)). In this study, for the DIN 18134 method, the E_{v1} value at the first loading step (66 MPa and 124 MPa) was taken as E_{50}^{ref} . Additionally, for the elastic rebound method, the Erebound value (181.9 MPa and 366.8 MPa) was taken as E_{50}^{ref} (to examine the variation in results).

Table 8. HS model parameters (based on elastic rebound and DIN 18134)

Parameters	Unit	5 Loading	5 Loading	4 Loading	4 Loading	Sub base (MH)
		(Erebound)	(Ev-DIN18134)	(Erebound)	(Ev-DIN18134)	
ϕ (°)	derece	40	40	42,5	42,5	30
ψ (°)	derece	10	10	10	10	0
C	kN/m ²	10	10	10	10	655
E_{50ref}	MPa	181.9	66	366.8	124	36
E_{ordref}	MPa	181.9	66	366.8	124	36
E_{urref}	MPa	545.7	192	1100.4	372	108
m	-	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,7
v	-	0,3	0,3	0,3	0,3	0,3
P_{ref}	kPa	100	100	100	100	100
R_f	-	0,9	0,9	0,9	0,9	0,9

Selection of E_{ur}^{ref} : In Plaxis software and in the literature, it is widely accepted that for granular soils, the E_{ur}^{ref} value can be taken as 3 to 5 times E_{50}^{ref} (Plaxis, 2023); (Schanz, Vermeer, & Bonnier, 1999). In this study, for simplicity and comparability, the rule $E_{ur}^{ref} = 3E_{50}^{ref}$ was applied. The HS parameters are given in Table 8.

2.5 Plaxis 3D Model and numerical analysis

Plaxis 3D is a commercial finite element method-based software developed for solving geotechnical engineering problems. The software includes various constitutive models (MC, HS, HSsmall, etc.) to model the nonlinear, time-dependent, and stress-strain behavior of soil and rock materials (Plaxis, 2023). The analysis logic basically consists of geometry creation, material definition, finite element mesh generation, phase definition, and solution stages. Plaxis 3D is widely used in geotechnical engineering for solving complex soil-structure interaction problems (Brinkgreve, Kumarswamy, & Swolfs, 2016). It provides reliable results especially in problems such as foundation design, slope stability, tunneling, and excavations.

The Plaxis 3D model created in this study was defined with dimensions of $x=3$ m, $y=3$ m, and total depth $z=1.5$ m, approximately 10 times the plate diameter (0.3 m). These dimensions are sufficient to minimize boundary effects (Bowles J. , 1997). The model was created as two layers:

Upper layer (0 – 0.5 m): Uniformly graded gravel (GW) fill

Lower layer (0.5 – 1.5 m): High-plasticity silt (MH) improved with hydraulic lime

In the model, the bottom boundary was fully fixed ($u_x=u_y=u_z=0$), while the lateral boundaries were fixed in the horizontal direction ($u_x=u_y=u_z=0$) with vertical movement allowed. The plate was defined as a "plate" element and modeled to behave rigidly. The plate thickness was 2.5 cm, and steel material properties ($E = 200$ GPa, $\nu = 0.3$) were assigned.

A "surface load" was selected in the numerical modeling for the following reasons:

The load applied to the plate in the field is a pressure transmitted through a hydraulic cylinder and uniformly distributed over the plate surface. "Surface load" represents this situation exactly (Plaxis, 2023).

With "surface load", the stress applied to the plate in each loading step can be directly defined, and the displacements obtained from the model can be compared with field data.

In the analyses, the stress values at each loading step were entered as a uniformly distributed load on the plate surface and the displacements obtained from the model were compared with the experimental displacements.

3. RESULTS

The settlements obtained from the Plaxis 3D analyses are presented comparatively together with the field test results in Table 9 - 12 and in the Figure 6 (a) and Figure 6 (b).

Table 9. Results of 5cycle loading test and MC model Plaxis results

Applied Max.Stress (kPa)	Measured S (mm)	Erebound (Mpa)	E_{v5} (DIN18134) (Mpa)
247	0,9	0.48	0.59
495	1,36	1.29	1.53
742	2,11	2.32	2.70
1485	4,75	6.25	7.16
1732	6,17	9.14	10.32

Table 10. Results of 5cycle loading test and HS model Plaxis results

Applied Max.Stress (kPa)	Measured S (mm)	Erebound (Mpa)	E_{v5} (DIN18134) (Mpa)
247	0,9	0.48	0.59
495	1,36	1.29	1.53
742	2,11	2.32	2.70

1485	4,75	6.25	7.16
1732	6,17	9.14	10.32

Tablo 11. Results of 4cycle loading test and MC model Plaxis results

Applied Max. Stress (kPa)	Measured S (mm)	Ereboun (Mpa)	E _{v,5} (DIN18134) (Mpa)
247	0,48	0.33	0.40
495	0,79	0,97	1.12
742	1,21	1,81	2.04
1485	2,68	5,13	5,64

Tablo 12. Results of 4cycle loading test and HS model Plaxis results

Applied Max. Stress (kPa)	Measured S (mm)	Ereboun (Mpa)	E _{v,5} (DIN18134) (Mpa)
247	0,48	0.47	1,09
495	1,79	1.15	2,50
742	1,21	1,91	4,09
1485	2,68	4,73	9,49

Figure 6. Comparative graph of the analysis and field results of the 5loading (a) and 4loading (b) tests

Also in the plate loading test with 5 loading cycles, the deformations obtained from the Plaxis 3D analysis using the MC and HS soil models at the maximum stress (1732 kN/m²) and in the plate loading test with 4 loading cycles, the deformations obtained from the Plaxis 3D analysis using the MC and HS soil models at the maximum stress (1485 kN/m²) are shown in figure 7 and figure 8.

Figure 7. Deformations obtained from Plaxis 3D analysis results for the 4 loading test at the maximum stress (1732 kN/m²) using MC and HS soil models:

(a) MC (Er=181,9 MPa), (b) MC (Ev5=130 MPa), (c) HS (E50=Ev=66 MPa), (d) HS (E50=Er=181,9 MPa)

Figure 8. Deformations obtained from Plaxis 3D analysis results for the 5 loading test at the maximum stress (1732 kN/m²) using MC and HS soil models:

(a) HS (ER=366.8 MPa), (b) HS (EV1=124 MPa), (c) MC (ER=366,8 MPa), (d) MC (EV4=252 MPa)

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 MC Model performance

When Tables 9-12 and Figures 5–6 presented under the Results section are evaluated together, the settlement curves calculated with the elastic rebound-based parameters ($E = 181.9$ MPa and 366.8 MPa) for both tests follow the experimental curve closely at low stress levels (247–742 kPa), but exceed the experimental curve at high stress levels (1485–1732 kPa). Particularly in the 5-loading test at 1732 kPa, a deviation of approximately 48% is observed with 9.14 mm (experimental: 6.17 mm). The parameters based on the final step of DIN 18134 ($E=130$ MPa and 252 MPa) gave higher settlements than the experimental values over the entire stress range, showing a deviation of 67% in the 5-loading test at the final step with 10.32 mm.

This indicates that due to the linear elastic-perfectly plastic nature of the MC model, it cannot adequately represent plastic deformations at high stresses, while the elastic rebound modulus performs well at low stresses.

4.2 HS Model performance

The curves obtained with the elastic rebound-based parameters ($E_{s0}=181.9$ MPa and 366.8 MPa) for the HS model are quite close to the experimental curves. In the 5-loading test, a deviation of 10% was observed at 247 kPa (0.81 mm computed vs. 0.90 mm measured), and a deviation of 61% at 1732 kPa (9.96 mm vs. 6.17 mm). In the 4-loading test, almost perfect agreement was observed at 247 kPa (0.47 mm vs. 0.48 mm), while a deviation of 76% was observed at 1485 kPa (4.73 mm vs. 2.68 mm).

The parameters based on the first step of DIN 18134 ($E_{50}=66$ MPa and 124 MPa) gave excessively high settlements over the entire stress range, showing a deviation of 194% in the 5-loading test at the final step (18.16 mm vs. 6.17 mm).

It is understood that the HS model performs very well at low stresses when using the elastic rebound parameters; however, the stress dependency exponent m should be calibrated specifically for the field conditions in order to reduce the deviation at high stresses.

4.3 Comparison of two methods

This comparison shows that the elastic rebound theory is more suitable for the HS model, while for the MC model, the closest results to the experimental data can be obtained with elastic rebound at low to medium stresses. However, neither method achieved perfect agreement over the entire stress range. This may be because both methods do not fully reflect the stress dependency of the soil. In the analyses performed with the stress dependency exponent $m=0.5$ for the HS model, using the elastic rebound values as E_{50}^{ref} was successful at low stresses but showed deviation at high stresses. This suggests that the m value should be calibrated specifically for the field conditions.

The distance of 30 m between the two test locations led to differences in the parameters. For example, the elastic rebound moduli were calculated as 181.9 MPa for the 5-loading test and 366.8 MPa for the 4-loading test. This reveals that the soil is heterogeneous in the horizontal direction and that the degree of compaction varies. To remain on the safe side in design, parameters that give lower stiffness (i.e., higher settlement) should be preferred. In this study, the 5-loading test data exhibited lower stiffness (181.9 MPa < 366.8 MPa); therefore, using these parameters will be safer. Table 13 shows performance situation for different methods.

Table 13. Comparative table of MC and HS model results

Methods	MC Model performance	HS model performance
Elastic rebound ($E_{rebound}$)	Good at low stresses, larger than experimental data at high stresses.	Very good at low stresses (2–10% deviation at 247 kPa), acceptable deviation at high stresses.
DIN 18134 (final loading E_{v5})	Above experimental values at all levels.	-
DIN 18134 (first loading E_{v1})	-	Excessively high settlements at all levels.

4.4 Recommendations

For the MC model: The best performance was obtained at low stresses using the elastic rebound modulus. To reduce the deviation at high stresses, the average of the elastic rebound modulus and the final-step E_v value (e.g., ~155 MPa for the 5-loading test) can be used.

For the HS model: Using the elastic rebound modulus as E_{50}^{ref} gave excellent results at low stresses. To reduce the deviation at high stresses:

The mm parameter should be calibrated specifically for the field conditions (e.g., $m=0.3-0.4$ could be tried).

Alternatively, the elastic rebound modulus should be taken as E_{ur}^{ref} , and E_{50}^{ref} should be taken from the final-step E_v value.

For both methods: To remain on the safe side, the parameters from the 5-loading test, which gives lower stiffness ($E_{rebound}=181.9$ MPa, $E_{v5}=130$ MPa), should be preferred.

5. RESULTS

The elastic rebound theory yielded $E_{rebound}=181.9$ MPa for the 5loading test and $E_{rebound}=366$ MPa for the 4loading test. According to DIN 18134, the E_v values at the final loading step (130 MPa for the 5loading test, 252 MPa for the 4-loading test) and at the first step (66 MPa and 124 MPa) were calculated.

In the MC model, the elastic rebound modulus gave settlements close to the experimental results at low stresses, while the deviation increased at high stresses. The final-step E_v value produced higher settlements at all stress levels.

In the HS model, using the elastic rebound modulus as E_{50}^{ref} provided excellent agreement at low stresses (0.81 mm computed vs. 0.90 mm measured at 247 kPa) and showed acceptable deviation at high stresses. The DIN 18134 E_{v1} values led to excessively high settlements.

The elastic rebound method was found to be successful in estimating the primary loading modulus for the HS model. To reduce the deviation at high stresses, site-specific calibration of the mm parameter is recommended.

The parameter differences between the two test locations (181.9 MPa vs. 366.8 MPa; 130 MPa vs. 252 MPa) indicate horizontal heterogeneity of the soil. To remain on the safe side, the parameters from the 5-loading test, which gives lower stiffness, should be preferred.

In engineering practice, it is recommended to use the elastic rebound modulus as E_{50}^{ref} for the HS model with $E_{ur}^{ref} = 3E_{50}^{ref}$ for the MC model, the average of the elastic rebound modulus and the final-step E_v value can be used.

Conflict of interest

There is no conflict to disclose.

Ethics and Consent to Participate declarations:

not applicable

Funding Declaration:

no funding

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This research is part of the first author's PhD thesis submitted to the Graduate School of Natural and Applied Sciences at Kocaeli University Turkiye.

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